

AI·EFFECT

Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility
For the Energy seCTor

D5.1: Strategy and Roadmap for AI-EFFECT

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Executive Summary

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming indispensable for the modernization, digitalisation, and decarbonisation of the European energy system. The AI-EFFECT project is developing a Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF) supporting this transformation. Its mission is to provide a trustworthy, scalable, and interoperable environment where AI solutions for energy applications can be tested, validated, benchmarked, and prepared for deployment under real-world conditions and in alignment with European regulations, including the AI Act and the Data Act. This deliverable D5.1 presents a comprehensive roadmap that defines the strategic evolution of AI-EFFECT across three time horizons—short, medium, and long term—ensuring the platform’s long-term viability, sustainability, and impact.

In the **short term (2024–2027)**, AI-EFFECT focuses on the complete deployment and validation of the platform across its four demonstrator nodes, covering district heating, congestion management, distributed energy resources (DER) integration, and energy community data spaces. Core functionalities include secure data management, modular and scalable architecture, interoperability through the VILLAS framework, and a suite of TEF services ranging from digital twins to trustworthiness algorithms for explainability and verification. The project also develops detailed documentation, onboarding material, test procedures, and monitoring mechanisms to support replicability. Coordination with sister TEFs (EnerTEF, EnergyGuard) and TEFs from other sectors, as well as alignment with EU regulatory requirements, establishes the foundation for a successful Energy TEF ecosystem.

In the **medium term (2027–2030)**, the roadmap shifts from development to consolidation, targeting the establishment of AI-EFFECT as a self-sustaining entity with a robust governance and business model. The platform will expand to new use cases of increasing relevance—such as data center management, flexibility markets, FLISR, dynamic line rating, hydrogen, nuclear SMRs—and introduce new TEF services including image processing, cyber-physical security assessment, and shared services aligned with other European energy TEFs. The AI-tool test will confront emerging computing technologies (LLMs, HPC GPUs, HIL/PHIL, blockchain) and enhanced documentation features, including multilingual support and LLM-enabled knowledge repositories. Coordination with non-energy TEFs and the formation of a European AI Energy Community will accelerate interoperability, community building, and methodological harmonisation.

In the **long term (2030–2035)**, AI-EFFECT is envisioned as a global reference infrastructure for trustworthy AI in energy, extending beyond Europe through collaboration with leading research institutes in the Americas, Asia, the Middle East, and Oceania. The TEF will support advanced use cases, such as AI-enabled resilience for extreme events, next-generation technologies - including quantum computing, robotics, IoT-edge intelligence - and European AI gigafactory ecosystems. Governance structures will be fully operational, enabling transparent monetisation and remuneration mechanisms. AI-EFFECT will contribute to international standards for AI in energy, host global competitions, conferences, and workshops, and act as a neutral coordinator of a Global Energy TEF network.

Overall, this roadmap positions AI-EFFECT as a cornerstone of Europe’s long-term strategy for deploying trustworthy, robust, and interoperable AI across the energy sector. By progressively expanding its technical capabilities, governance framework, and international reach, AI-EFFECT supports the safe integration of AI into European energy systems, accelerates innovation, and reinforces Europe’s leadership in reliable and consumer-centric AI technologies.

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI-EFFECT	Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility for the Energy Sector
AIoD	AI On Demand
CEN-CENELEC	European Committee for Standardization - European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ETIP SNET	European Technology & Innovation Platform – Smart Networks for Energy Transition
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HEMS	Home Energy Management Systems
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IoT	Internet-of-Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LLM	Large Language Model
MIM	Minimal Interoperability Mechanism
PdM	Predictive Maintenance
SEF	Semantic Interoperability Framework
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facility

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly becoming a transformative technology for the energy sector, enabling improved forecasting, optimization, automation, and decision-making across the energy value chain. However, deploying AI solutions in real operational environments requires reliable infrastructures where these technologies can be tested, validated, and demonstrated under realistic conditions while ensuring compliance with regulatory, technical, and ethical requirements. In response to this need, the European Union has established **Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs)** as large-scale infrastructures designed to support the development, testing, and validation of trustworthy AI applications across strategic sectors.

Within this framework, **AI-EFFECT (Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility for the Energy Sector)** contributes to the European TEF ecosystem by providing a dedicated environment for the testing and experimentation of AI solutions in energy systems. The project develops a distributed platform that integrates data, digital infrastructures, and testing services to support AI developers, energy stakeholders, and research organizations in validating AI technologies across several energy-related use cases. By enabling experimentation under realistic operational conditions, AI-EFFECT supports the deployment of trustworthy AI solutions and facilitates their adoption within the European energy system.

Importantly, TEFs are not intended as short-term research infrastructures but rather as strategic instruments in the long-term European vision for AI deployment. Through the Horizon Europe and Digital Europe programmes, the European Union is building a permanent ecosystem of experimentation facilities that support innovation, strengthen industrial competitiveness, and ensure that AI technologies are developed and deployed according to European values and regulatory frameworks. In the energy domain, TEFs are expected to play a growing role in accelerating the integration of AI into energy systems, supporting the energy transition, and enabling collaboration between AI developers, infrastructure operators, and policymakers.

In this context, AI-EFFECT should not be regarded as an isolated project that concludes at the end of its funded period. Instead, it represents one component of a broader and long-term European strategy aimed at establishing sustainable infrastructures for AI innovation. Consequently, the long-term viability and impact of AI-EFFECT depend on the ability to extend its results beyond the project lifetime, ensuring that the platform, services, and community developed during the project continue to evolve and contribute to the European AI ecosystem.

For this reason, this deliverable defines a **strategic roadmap** for the evolution and sustainability of AI-EFFECT beyond the project duration. The roadmap identifies concrete objectives and development directions that address multiple dimensions, including technological development, governance and sustainability, expansion of services and use cases, ecosystem coordination, and community engagement. By defining these goals, the roadmap supports the transition of AI-EFFECT from a research project into a long-term experimentation infrastructure aligned with European AI policies and initiatives.

To structure this strategic vision, the roadmap is organized into three time horizons:

- **Short-term goals (until project end, 2027)** focus on the completion and validation of the AI-EFFECT platform, including the deployment of nodes, implementation of TEF services, development of documentation, and initial coordination with the European TEF ecosystem.
- **Medium-term goals (2027–2030)** address the consolidation of AI-EFFECT as a sustainable entity, including the expansion of use cases and services, the integration of emerging technologies, the development of governance and business models, and stronger engagement with European standards and communities.
- **Long-term goals (beyond 2030)** envision the evolution of AI-EFFECT within a mature international ecosystem of AI experimentation infrastructures, incorporating advanced computing technologies, expanded global collaboration, and the establishment of widely adopted standards and services for AI in the energy sector.

The remainder of this deliverable is structured as follows. **Section 2** presents the **short-term roadmap (2024–2027)**, focusing on the deployment and validation of the AI-EFFECT platform and its services, together with documentation, ecosystem coordination, and stakeholder engagement activities. **Section 3** describes the **medium-term roadmap (2027–2030)**, outlining the expansion of use cases, the development of new TEF services, the adoption of emerging computing technologies, and the establishment of governance mechanisms for a self-sustaining AI-EFFECT ecosystem. **Section 4** presents the **long-term roadmap (beyond 2030)**, which explores future developments including additional nodes, new technological paradigms, global coordination of AI experimentation infrastructures, and the emergence of international standards for AI in energy systems. Finally, **Section 5** summarizes the main conclusions and strategic perspectives derived from the roadmap.

Together, as shown in the figure below, these sections provide a structured vision for how AI-EFFECT can evolve from a project-based initiative into a long-lasting experimentation infrastructure supporting the development and deployment of trustworthy AI solutions for the European energy sector.

Powering the Future: Europe’s AI Roadmap for Smart Grids

This roadmap guides the European energy sector in adopting AI, aligning with the EU’s comprehensive ‘AI Continent Action Plan’. It presents a phased approach to build capacity, scale solutions, and achieve a fully optimized, AI-enabled smart grid, ensuring the energy transition benefits from trustworthy and innovative technology.

1.1 Overview of related efforts in TEF

The European Technology & Innovation Platforms, Smart Networks for Energy Transition (ETIP SNET) [1] published in April 2025 the position paper “Unlocking the Potential of AI and Generative AI in European Smart Grids” [1], which proposes goals and a roadmap for the use of AI in the European energy grids. Given the commonality of objectives with this AI-EFFECT deliverable, content comparison has been carried out, highlighting similarities and differences; the outcomes are reported in the table below.

Time-frame	AI-EFFECT Goals	ETIP SNET Goals	Similarities	Differences / Gaps
Short-Term (0-2 years)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deploy AI-EFFECT platform with core functionalities: secure, modular, scalable. • Implement node demonstrations for 4 use cases (district heating, congestion management, DER integration, energy communities). • Develop service catalogue & certification criteria. • Ensure compliance with EU AI Act & data-sharing regulations. • Documentation for onboarding, test procedures, digitalization of use cases. • Interconnection with EU TEFs & AIoD. • Community interaction board & trustworthiness algorithms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with EU AI governance structures (AI Office, AI Act Service Desk). • Pilot regulatory sandboxes for AI in energy. • Launch Data Labs & secure data-sharing pilots. • Develop synthetic data tools. • Fund priority AI pilots (PdM, cybersecurity, forecasting). • Initiate workforce upskilling via AI Skills Academy. • Pilot explainable AI & interim trust labels. • Establish TEFs & edge computing pilots. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both focus on platform readiness, data governance, compliance with AI Act, and pilot projects. • Emphasis on documentation & trust mechanisms. • Early collaboration with EU initiatives, both regarding TEFs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETIP SNET adds regulatory sandboxes, AI maturity frameworks, and consumer trust campaigns. • AI-EFFECT focuses more on technical deployment and node-specific use cases. • ETIP SNET includes open innovation programs and SME support, missing in AI-EFFECT.
Medium-Term (2-5 years)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish AI-EFFECT as a self-sustaining entity. • Add new nodes/services (district heating, data centers, flexibility markets). • Enable multi-language support & LLM-based knowledge repository. • Develop governance & monetization models. • Expand interoperability across grids & countries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale interoperable AI systems across EU grids. • Implement EU-wide AI certification & labelling. • Expand federated learning & HPC/edge infrastructure. • Develop sector-specific 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both aim for scaling AI systems, interoperability, standards, and governance models. • Focus on expanding infrastructure & nodes. • Emphasis on competitions & community engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETIP SNET stresses harmonisation across EU, formal certification, and consumer trust frameworks. • AI-EFFECT lacks explicit Green AI and energy efficiency goals.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribute to international standards. • Organize AI competitions for energy. 	<p>foundational models.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote Green AI & energy-efficient hardware. • Update grid codes for AI-driven operations. • Build collaborative ecosystems & consumer trust programs. • Deploy MIM standards & strengthen cybersecurity. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETIP SNET includes co-funded deployment programs and public-private partnerships, absent in AI-EFFECT.
<p>Long-Term (5+ years)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monetization & remuneration fully implemented. • Integration with EU HPC network. • Global TEF ecosystem coordination. • Quantum computing & robotics integration. • AI-powered resilience (threat detection, disaster response). • Establish global standards & centers of excellence. • Expand nodes internationally (Asia, Americas). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieve deep AI integration & semi-autonomous grids. • Institutionalise governance & accountability frameworks. • Deploy advanced AI (robust, explainable, uncertainty-aware). • Optimise AI energy footprint (TinyML, neuromorphic chips). • Lead global AI standards & alliances. • Ensure fairness, transparency, and alignment with EU Green Deal. • Enable cross-border AI-driven energy trade. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both target global leadership, advanced AI integration, and standards harmonisation. • Emphasis on HPC & quantum computing. - Focus on resilience & cybersecurity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETIP SNET prioritises ethical alignment, consumer rights, and Green Deal compliance. • AI-EFFECT roadmap is more technology-centric, less on societal frameworks. • ETIP SNET includes lifelong learning & global alliances, missing in AI-EFFECT.

2 Strategic Roadmap: Short-Term Goals 2024-2027

The initial section of the roadmap addresses the time interval that is running until the conclusion of AI-EFFECT project, set at its Month 36 and corresponding to September 2027. Main goal of this stage is the public provision of the AI-EFFECT platform, which will be deployed and tested with respect to its use cases in the demonstrator nodes.

For this reason, the roadmap in the short-term stage is focused on the characteristics and tested features of the AI-EFFECT platform, in combination with its documentation. Additional aspects that reinforce the maturity level as well as exploitability of the delivered platform correspond to the cooperation with other TEFs projects and initiatives, in the same energy domain as well as in other neighbour ones.

The following sub-sections address in detail the specific goals, grouped in five distinctive categories: (i) AI-EFFECT Platform implementation, (ii) AI-EFFECT services, (iii) documentation, (iv) EU ecosystem coordination and (v) user interaction and community.

2.1 AI-EFFECT Platform Implementation

The deployment of the AI-EFFECT platform needs for the achievement of multiple objectives that go beyond the release of minimum functional requirements. The future adoption of the platform, beyond the project environment (i.e., for additional use cases and involving new AI vendors), depends on the analysis of overall aspects, in the development phase of the project, and the implementation of required features in the most appropriate manner.

2.1.1 Core functionalities of the AI-EFFECT platform

Rationale:	Set up foundational platform for a unified testing and experimental facility for energy sectors, while keeping it intuitive for a large audience, focused on data security and transparency.
Description:	<p>The following are core functionalities of the AI-EFFECT platform, to ensure the reliable and efficient functioning of implemented services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection of sensitive data through robust authentication, role-based access control, and comprehensive logging mechanisms. • Guarantee of reproducibility and traceability by maintaining version-controlled test configurations and detailed audit trails. It allows for independent verification and replication of every test. • Implementation of a modular architecture built around standardized interfaces, that supports integration of new testing modules. • Assurance of scalable performance as data volumes and system complexity increase. • Provision of intuitive interfaces. • Provision of support for formal methods—such as automated model checking and theorem proving—to validate critical AI components.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	The complete description of operating principles is contained in the AI-EFFECT deliverable D1.2 “Operating Principles”. It provides guidelines and references for the implementation of such functionalities in the TEF.
Means of verification:	The WP4, “AI-EFFECT Infrastructure Deployment and Validation”, consists of the implementation of the platform. The WP4 deliverables, especially the deliverable D4.2 “AI-EFFECT final version and setup”, will describe in detail the achievements.

2.1.2 Data Exchange and Interoperability

Rationale:	The development of effective AI is critically dependent on access to large, high-quality datasets. However, energy data is often siloed, of varying quality, or restricted due to privacy and commercial sensitivities, creating a significant bottleneck for innovation.
Description:	Regarding technical aspects, several EU initiatives focus on data spaces ranging from development to use and integration. By establishing a structured environment where diverse data sources can be integrated and accessed, data spaces enable the seamless sharing and utilization of datasets across different AI applications. This enhances the robustness of AI models by allowing them to be trained and tested on a wider variety of data. AI-EFFECT will contribute to interoperability and integration possibilities of data spaces by demonstrating automated access and integration as well as real-time communication between data space and users. For instance, one way is the integration of data space in existing communication frameworks, like VILLASnode. The communication framework provides the translation between different tools, protocols or data formats, and serves as gateway to the data space to provide and access data in an automated way. The use of dedicated APIs, metadata and common vocabularies further simplify the data transaction among different actors of the TEFs.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	An infrastructural layer within AI-EFFECT is being implemented, establishing the data communication framework for distributed TEFs. Such framework makes use of VILLASframework, extended with data space connectors for the TEF.
Means of verification:	The WP2 “AI-EFFECT Architecture and Building Blocks Design” will work on the implementation of data exchange solutions, especially in the Task 2.3 “Extending and preparing infrastructural building blocks for the Cyber-Physical TEF” and its deliverable D2.3 “AI-EFFECT Infrastructural Building Blocks”.

2.1.3 Demonstration of Nodes

Rationale:	Ensure compliance of the services to meet technical and regulatory mechanisms as well as standards, while ensuring the platform dynamically adapts to the evolving energy system requirements.
Description:	<p>AI-EFFECT ensures the feasible deployment of new AI services by adopting a modular and extensible architecture that supports seamless integration of additional nodes and pipelines. The platform employs language- and protocol-agnostic interfaces, allowing new services from vendors or research groups to be onboarded without extensive reconfiguration.</p> <p>The adherence to core functionalities of AI-EFFECT, referred to in the Section 2.1.1 of this document, ensures the eligibility of the newly proposed services.</p> <p>Through containerization and alignment with Minimal Interoperability Mechanisms (MIMs), services can be rapidly tested, benchmarked, and orchestrated alongside existing components. Dedicated validation and monitoring procedures assess scalability, performance, and compliance, guaranteeing that newly introduced services meet both technical requirements and regulatory standards. This approach ensures that the platform remains dynamic and adaptable, enabling the continuous enrichment of the AI service catalogue and supporting innovation in the evolving energy ecosystem.</p>

Implementation guidelines for the TEF	In WP3, the building blocks are containerized, allowing for the full deployment of the AI-EFFECT platform that consists of (i) the open-source orchestrator, and (ii) the fully integrated and test-ready AI service pipelines along with corresponding data sources.
Means of verification	The WP3 deliverables, particularly D3.1 “AI services Onboarding and AI-EFFECT catalogue” [3], D3.2 “Microservice Orchestration” and D3.3 “AI-EFFECT platform Testing and Assessment” are reporting on these achievements.

2.1.4 Availability and Maintenance of AI-EFFECT platform

Rationale:	Define the governance mechanisms and business models that ensures the replicability and exploitation of the AI-EFFECT platform after project conclusion. In particular, the maintainability of the AI-EFFECT solutions made publicly available.
Description:	<p>The availability, accessibility, and maintenance of the AI-EFFECT platform and its services beyond the lifetime of the project are directly related to the broader governance and sustainability strategy part. The strategy that will be developed will addresses both the technical and organizational dimensions of sustainability, while remaining adaptable to evolving regulatory and market conditions.</p> <p>The most important aspect, to ensure continuity of AI-EFFECT platform, is the establishment of its governance beyond the contractual project lifetime. This will include clarifying ownership of the platform modules, data contributions, and user-generated outputs. Options under consideration include centralized operation by a designated legal entity, distributed stewardship by a consortium of stakeholders, or integration with existing European AI/energy initiatives. The final governance model will prioritize inclusiveness, neutrality, and alignment with EU-level strategies. Potential models include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pay-per-use, providing cost-efficient access for researchers and SMEs with limited budgets. • Subscription-based access, offering predictability for frequent users and institutional adopters. • Sponsorship and partnerships, enabling private and public actors to contribute to the sustainability of the platform. • Pay-to-certify services, creating value-added opportunities for AI vendors seeking trusted validation of their solutions. <p>Moreover, the technical maintenance and upgradability of the platform will be ensured with: (i) regular updates to maintain compatibility with evolving AI frameworks and energy sector standards, (ii) security patches and monitoring to ensure compliance with data protection and cybersecurity regulations and (iii) modular upgrades that allow independent improvement of individual components without disrupting the platform as a whole.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	Task 5.3 “AI-EFFECT business model and governance structure to ensure long-term economic viability” analyses governance and ownership models. AI-EFFECT consortium will, within the indicated task, assess and propose a governance structure that defines roles and responsibilities for the platform’s operation, maintenance, and evolution.
Means of verification:	The governance aspects will be addressed in the Task 5.3 and concretized in the deliverable D5.3 “Assessment and Recommendations for the Governance, Ownership-Operational and Business Models”, which will refer to legal and regulatory considerations, including the EU AI Act, and other sectorial TEFs.

2.2 AI-EFFECT Services

The main objective of AI-EFFECT, as a TEF, is the deployment and maintenance of services that help development of AI tools, also fostering their integration with the energy systems. The TEF services must be accessible, easy to be deployed, respectful of regulations, comprehensive in terms of needs for the AI tools developers. The TEF service catalogue must be, moreover, expandible to cover new service needs will arise in the near future.

2.2.1 Catalogue of Services

Rationale:	Main goal of AI-EFFECT, as a TEF, is to offer services for the testing and validation of AI-based tools, or some specific features of them, to the developers. At this scope, it is necessary to deploy a variegated catalogue that contains all the necessary services, covering all aspects required by AI-tool market.
Description	<p>AI-EFFECT will achieve a comprehensive catalogue of AI services by designing and deploying an orchestrated platform that integrates containerized AI solutions, data sources, and certification mechanisms into interoperable pipelines. Through close dialogue with AI vendors and alignment with standard platform interfaces such as AIoD (AI On Demand) [1], the project ensures that services are modular, composable, and accessible via a structured catalogue documented with trustworthiness assessments (e.g., AI-Builder [2], ALTAI - Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence [3]).</p> <p>Orchestration mechanisms developed within the project enable efficient management of diverse services—ranging from digital twins and semantic interconnectors to certification nodes—while maintaining scalability, security, and interoperability. Rigorous testing and monitoring phases validate functionality, robustness, and performance, ensuring that all services can be reliably deployed in real-world use cases across the energy value chain.</p> <p>By documenting procedures and making services accessible through marketplaces and demonstration sites, AI-EFFECT establishes a transparent, trustworthy, and expandable catalogue that supports broad adoption and long-term exploitation across the European energy ecosystem. Anyway, in this phase, not all the services will be directly reusable with plug-and-play approach; on the contrary, they will have to be readapted because of their specificity with respect to use cases and nodes. The following phases of AI-EFFECT roadmap (medium- and long-term) will overcome this limitation.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	The services, defined by the AI-EFFECT nodes, are onboarded into the AIoD platform to design the solutions using the Design Studio provided by the AIoD platform itself. This procedure provides the foundation for standardising the AI pipeline for the AI-EFFECT project by accomplishing the onboarding and containerization, hence leading to the creation of the AI-EFFECT catalogue.
Means of verification	The task 3.1 and its deliverable D3.1 “AI services Onboarding and AI-EFFECT catalogue” [3] documents the procedure for creating catalogues for onboarding AI services, detailing standardized interfaces, technical requirements, and specifications for integration into the AIoD platform.

2.2.2 Requirements and Specifications for the TEF Use Cases

Rationale:	The definition of TEF use cases allows describing the nodes and the TEF services that are developed and tested. Using a common approach for describing the various nodes ensures quality targets are met and replicability.
Description	<p>Within the duration of the project, four nodes will be implemented to demonstrate the capabilities of the AI-EFFECT platform. These nodes will cover different use cases of AI tools in the energy industry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Danish node: District heating and sector coupling • Dutch node: Transmission system congestion management • German node: Distributed energy resources (DER) integration in distribution system • Portuguese node: Energy community data space <p>The use cases of the industry are further specified as business use cases. Each of the nodes implements one or more testing workflows that integrate several TEF services, called TEF test use cases, aiming at testing the AI tools developed for the business use cases.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	The TEF test use cases (connected to the services) and the corresponding business use cases are documented by the TEF test use case templates, based on the HE AI4REALNET [6] MS Word template adapted from ISO/IEC TR 24030 [7]. Each node is described by: (i) the narrative of the TEF test use case, (ii) the corresponding business use case, (iii) the challenges and mitigation, (iv) the future scope.
Means of verification	The complete, detailed descriptions of AI-EFFECT use cases are found in D1.1 “Design of AI-EFFECT Use Cases and outputs” [9].

2.2.3 AI-EFFECT Trustworthiness Algorithms

Rationale:	The massive proliferation of AI tools asks for stringent requirements regarding the quality of the tool outputs; AI-EFFECT introduces explainability algorithms for assessing the trustworthiness of the tested tools.
Description	<p>The project will develop mathematical certification algorithms and explainability algorithms that enhance the trustworthiness of AI solutions in the energy sector.</p> <p>Explainability algorithms will be designed for use both during the training of AI models and during inference. In both cases, they help users understand how individual features, or combinations of features, affect the model’s predictions. As part of AI EFFECT, these algorithms will be applied to forecasting, optimization, and control tools.</p> <p>Certification algorithms will provide mathematical guarantees on the performance of AI tools by using correctness verification methods. These algorithms compare the AI model’s output against a physical benchmark and quantify either the deviation from or the worst-case violation of that benchmark. They will be developed specifically for optimization and control tasks.</p> <p>In addition, the project may explore worst-case prediction algorithms for forecasting applications. These algorithms aim to identify the conditions under which AI model predictions become most extreme, helping users anticipate and manage high-risk scenarios.</p>

Implementation guidelines for the TEF	AI-EFFECT deploys two algorithms to enhance AI transparency and reliability: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The AI interpretability algorithm will build upon established methods (e.g., SHAP) to explain how inputs influence model outputs, enabling users to understand the reasoning behind predictions and to construct surrogate models for complex processes. 2) The AI verification algorithm will assess compliance with user-defined specifications and physical system constraints, providing assurances about safe and reliable real-world operation.
Means of verification	The AI explainability and verification algorithms are accessible in these GitHub repositories [10]- [11], with related documentation, corresponding to the project deliverable D1.3.

2.2.4 Rules for Deployment of New Services

Rationale:	AI-EFFECT is structured around specific objectives for the development and test of 14 TEF services. However, the architecture of AI-EFFECT platform has to be designed by considering the inclusion of new services by the TEF owners, as part of medium and long term goals.
Description:	<p>AI-EFFECT ensures the feasible deployment of new AI services by adopting a modular and extensible architecture that supports seamless integration of additional nodes and pipelines. The platform employs language- and protocol-agnostic interfaces, allowing new services from vendors or research groups to be onboarded without extensive reconfiguration.</p> <p>The adherence to core functionalities of AI-EFFECT, referred to in the Section 2.1.1 of this document, ensures the eligibility of the newly proposed services.</p> <p>Through containerization and alignment with Minimum Interoperability Mechanisms (MIMs), services can be rapidly tested, benchmarked, and orchestrated alongside existing components. Dedicated validation and monitoring procedures assess scalability, performance, and compliance, guaranteeing that newly introduced services meet both technical requirements and regulatory standards. This approach ensures that the platform remains dynamic and adaptable, enabling the continuous enrichment of the AI service catalogue and supporting innovation in the evolving energy ecosystem.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	<p>The architecture leverages the Semantic Interoperability Framework (SEF) for the knowledge federation and decentralized data exchange based on ontologies among AI-IoT edge/cloud nodes. Moreover, a Security-by-Design strategy establishes a resilient trust framework spanning compute, storage, and processing layers.</p> <p>Attaining this goal requires adopting a zero-trust architecture combined with an efficient zero-touch deployment and configuration approach, delivering enhanced security without introducing major cost overheads.</p>
Means of verification:	The AI-EFFECT Architecture Design, with structural concepts for the scalability to include new TEF services, is described in D2.1.

2.3 Documentation

While the technical capabilities of the platform are central to its value, the long-term and successful exploitation and replicability of AI-EFFECT outputs - by vendors, specialists and researchers in the energy sector - critically depends on the availability of comprehensive, accessible, and well-maintained documentation.

Since the user groups that will access the AI-EFFECT platform will own different backgrounds, technical competencies, and goals, the documentation aim to make the stakeholders (i) understand the platform's

capabilities and architecture, (ii) set up and operate the system independently and (iii) identify how to integrate and test the AI solutions and datasets.

2.3.1 Onboarding and Use of AI-EFFECT platform

Rationale:	Ensure that external users, especially the AI tool developers, smoothly manage to access the AI-EFFECT platform and perform the authorized actions.
Description:	Clear onboarding and well-structured documentation are paramount to ensure that new users can effectively adopt the AI-EFFECT platform. This onboarding experience is expected to be easy and accessible, regardless of the users' expertise or technical background. Onboarding materials should explain how users can access and configure the necessary resources to use the TEF.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	Documentation materials should go beyond onboarding and cover the full utilization of the TEF, so that the users can thoroughly test their AI models while experiencing the full capabilities of the platform. Still, these materials are expected to evolve, not only to reflect best practices, guided by ongoing developments, but also by incorporating a continuous improvement methodology of the TEF, which will be based on the feedback of the users themselves. Therefore, it is expected that the project will develop a knowledge base, as well as training resources and programs, that provide structured learning pathways for the users. This approach ensures that TEF documentation is a living resource that adapts to new use cases, incorporates emerging data, and offers practical guidance to AI vendors and other types of users.
Means of verification:	Documentation material is related to the deliverables D4.2 "AI-EFFECT final version and setup" and D4.3 "Main findings and lessons learned".

2.3.2 Descriptions of Use Cases Test Procedures

Rationale:	AI-EFFECT project aims at facilitating the execution of TEF services, supporting the AI tool developers. At this scope, proper documentation on the test procedures favours the involvement of new AI tool developers as AI-EFFECT users.
Description	This documentation specifies how the TEF infrastructure is configured and scaled, how external AI providers can integrate and test their solutions, and how use cases are validated end-to-end across the energy value chain. It also formalizes testing workflows in alignment with European standards and regulations such as the AI Act and GDPR, while incorporating iterative processes for continuous feedback from partners, providers, and end-users. Furthermore, the documentation will include procedures for benchmarking performance, assessing trustworthiness, and managing ethical and data governance risks using frameworks such as ALTAI. By capturing these elements in a structured and transparent manner, AI-EFFECT provides replicable guidance that enables stakeholders to understand, reproduce, and improve the testing process, ensuring that the platform remains reliable, trustworthy, and exploitable beyond the lifetime of the project.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	In AI-EFFECT, Task 4.2 achievements will ensure the creation of detailed documentation describing the test procedures that govern the deployment, validation, and ethical assessment of AI solutions within the AI-EFFECT platform.
Means of verification	Task 4.2 of AI-EFFECT, and its deliverable D4.2 "AI-EFFECT final version and setup" describes the details of the test procedures.

2.3.3 Automated, digitalized monitoring of Use Cases

Rationale:	The use cases tested in AI-EFFECT needs for dedicated and advanced monitoring solutions that manage to evaluate test performances and improve the platform components.
Description	AI-EFFECT carries out the digitalization of use cases by integrating real and synthetic data sources, digital twins, and semantic interconnectors into orchestrated testing pipelines that replicate conditions across the energy value chain. Each use case is deployed within the TEF platform as a controlled, reproducible environment where AI services can be validated against sector-specific requirements. In parallel, the project ensures systematic documentation of developed AI services, capturing their containerized structure, functional specifications, and compliance with standards and regulations.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	The documentation to be provided includes benchmarking results, performance monitoring, and trustworthiness assessments based on frameworks such as ALTAI. By coupling digitalized use cases with transparent and structured documentation, AI-EFFECT provides stakeholders with reliable guidance on how services operate, interact, and scale, thus enabling their reusability, comparability, and adoption across diverse energy applications.
Means of verification	The aspects and documentation indicated above are part of the deliverables D3.4 “AI-EFFECT Scalability report” and D4.3 “Main findings and lessons learned”.

2.4 EU Ecosystem Coordination

AI-EFFECT takes place in a dynamic environment, constituted by several TEF initiatives, in the energy domain and in others, with increasing attention on the development of AI tools. For this reason, strong collaboration with existing TEFs as well as EU regulations on the AI tool development is fundamental.

2.4.1 Interconnection with Other EU Energy TEFs

Rationale:	Due to their high potential in fostering AI tool developments, TEFs are gaining increasing importance in several sectors beyond energy. Hence, AI-EFFECT aims at deepening knowledge and technology exchange with other TEFs, in energy as well as in other domains.
Description:	In addition to the technical deployments, accompanied by their documentation as well as non-functional features, AI-EFFECT aims to exploit the continuous and close collaboration with the projects EnerTEF [4] and EnergyGuard [5], belonging to the same Horizon Europe call of AI-EFFECT, to strengthen the European ecosystem of TEFs for AI in the energy domain. Moreover, collaboration with TEFs in other domains are related to the projects in the Digital Europe programme; specifically, the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) CoordinaTEF runs a cluster of TEFs in the smart cities (CitCom.ai), agri-food (agrifoodTEF), health-care (TEF-Health) and manufacturing (AI-Matters) domains.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	With respect to TEFs in the energy domain (EnerTEF and EnergyGuard), the action points being implemented are described hereafter. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A coordinated catalogue of services will be developed to provide end-users with a clear overview of the complementary functionalities offered by each TEF. This catalogue will facilitate navigation, highlight specialized services, and promote interoperability across platforms.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The consortium will share best practices on business models, including pay-per-use, subscription schemes, certification services, and sponsorship approaches. This will allow each project to learn from the others and identify sustainable and accessible strategies for long-term operation. • AI-EFFECT, EnerTEF, and EnergyGuard will jointly establish standardized procedures for testing and certification. These procedures will ensure that AI tools are validated in consistent, transparent, and comparable ways, and that results from one TEF are recognized by others. • Collaboration will also focus on joint policy recommendations, particularly concerning the AI Act and trustworthy AI requirements in the energy sector. Insights from project pilots will feed into aligned positions for regulatory bodies, supporting conformity assessment and certification frameworks. <p>This collaborative approach will reduce duplication of effort, promote interoperability, and strengthen trust in TEF services.</p> <p>The cooperation with the TEFs in the other sectors is capitalized by the collaboration with CoordinaTEF, in particular the active participation with their working groups on business models, TEF services and stakeholder engagement. Mutual participation in sectorial or joint dissemination events consolidate the knowledge exchange.</p>
Means of verification	The activities reported above are described, with specific details, in the deliverable D6.5 “Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities - Interim report” and D6.7 “Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities - Final report”.

2.4.2 Compliance with EU AI & Data Sharing Regulations

Rationale:	The implementation of a vast multitude of AI tools is reaching an incredibly high speed, while related standards, policies and regulations are under development. AI-EFFECT must adhere to the latests regulations on AI and Data Sharing to ensure the adoption of its solutions.
Description:	<p>AI EFFECT focuses on gaining an in-depth understanding of the legal and regulatory risks associated with the use of AI in the energy sector. Specifically, the project identifies and reviews relevant literature and create a regulatory risk framework that will serve to inform regulatory compliance procedures.</p> <p>In addition, AI-EFFECT aims to identify key regulatory barriers and enablers for the uptake of AI in the energy sector by conducting interviews with practitioners working at TSOs, DSOs, and AI vendors.</p> <p>As a result, AI-EFFECT will be well-aware and enabled to navigate the regulatory risks.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	Specific rules from the EU regulations in use, as AI Act and the Data Act, are analysed, allowing for evaluation of AI-EFFECT platform suitability with respect to its technical features and governance aspects.
Means of verification:	Related findings are included in a research paper to be published and in the deliverable D5.2 “Regulatory and Legal Risk Assessment and Policy Recommendations”.

2.5 User Interaction and Community

Success of AI-EFFECT depends on the adoption of the developed platform and services. At this scope, the dissemination and exploitation of project achievements is of paramount importance. The engagement with AI-EFFECT stakeholders must be tailored to their needs and role in the energy systems, in order to carry out the most effective and impactful use of AI-EFFECT solutions.

2.5.1 AI-EFFECT Dissemination and Exploitation

Rationale:	AI-EFFECT solutions must be disseminated to ensure the replicability, engagement of TEF service users and, overall, to guarantee the self-sustainability of the platform beyond the grant period (as HE project).
Description:	Communication activities, in particular their type and content, must be tailored to the target groups of stakeholders that AI-EFFECT interacts with.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	<p>A Communication & Dissemination plan, supported by content developed across the project's duration, will be established, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • project visual identity: project logo, public website (created and populated with comprehensive project information and updated regularly), templates (e.g., presentations, reports, posters, letters), project brochure/flyer; • online communication activities: website materials, social media posts (via both project and partner channels), digital newsletters (highlighting key outcomes and updates featured on the website); • infographics/fact sheets: visually engaging, information-rich assets presenting key project components, including promotional videos.
Means of verification:	The activities reported above are described, with specific details, in the deliverable D6.3 "Initial dissemination and Communication Plan", D6.5 "Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities - Interim report" and D6.7 "Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities - Final report".

2.5.2 AI-EFFECT End-End User Profiling and Storyboards

Rationale:	AI-EFFECT platform interacts with a great variety of stakeholders: AI tool developers, technology providers, energy generators and distributors, certification bodies and policy developers.
Description:	AI-EFFECT platform develops specific interaction mechanisms, corresponding to different authentication and authorization methods and rights, adapted to the specific type of stakeholder as platform user. Such interaction mechanisms correspond to different profile users, which originates from platform use motivation: grid operators share data and evaluate the AI tool results, AI tool developers need for the execution of TEF services, while test laboratories offer their infrastructure for the TEF service execution.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT develops knowledge-sharing activities, including webinars, conferences, and online forums, to enable discussion and the exchange of insights among policymakers, researchers, industry representatives, and citizens. These actions create avenues for ongoing learning, the dissemination of best practices, and stakeholder networking, supporting a cooperative environment for policy design and execution.
Means of verification:	The results of the described activities are reported in the deliverable D6.7 "Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities - Final report".

3 Strategic Roadmap: Medium-Term goals 2027-2030

The second section of the roadmap addresses the time interval that is running from the conclusion of AI-EFFECT project, corresponding to September 2027, for the successive 3 years. Main goal of this stage is the use of AI-EFFECT platform and its TEF services, which have been developed and tested in the project lifetime, by external stakeholders, especially by AI tool developers.

For this reason, the roadmap in the medium-term stage is focused on the establishment of the AI-EFFECT as an entity that is self-maintained, from the economic and governance viewpoint, with an effective business strategy. In order to keep the pace with the fast developments in the AI sector, the TEF services must be expanded and consider new use cases and nodes, beyond the ones tested in AI-EFFECT lifetime.

The following sub-sections address in detail the specific goals, grouped in seven distinctive categories: (i) new nodes potential to add, (ii) new TEF services, (iii) new compute technology, (iv) AI-EFFECT platform, (v) documentation, (vi) standards and regulation for Europe and (vii) user interaction and community.

3.1 New Use Cases Potential to Add

This section explores the additional use cases, currently not included in the AI-EFFECT activities due to limitation of resources and the strategic decisions on the areas to be focused on, which can be tested in additional AI-EFFECT nodes. The rationale for the selection of the use cases described below corresponds to the increased relevance of such use cases or their necessity of AI tools, to enhance the energy-related technology or solution.

3.1.1 District Heating

Rationale:	There is a significant potential for implementing power-to-heat solutions in district heating systems.
Description:	<p>Heat pumps, electric boilers, and heat storage technologies can be used to convert power to heat when electricity is cheap and reduce the need for heat in periods where it is expensive (i.e., when it is scarce). District heating grid operators can, for instance, use this flexibility to provide ancillary services to power grid operators, and this potential was recently assessed in [1]</p> <p>The flexibility can either be obtained through <i>direct</i> technologies such as intermediate heat storage or <i>indirectly</i> through demand-side flexibility, i.e., by incentivizing heat consumers (households, commercial buildings, and industry) to shift their demand [2]. Again, the flexibility of the heat consumers can be obtained through direct agreements between the operator and the consumer (e.g., greenhouses may be asked by the operator to adjust their demand within some time frame) or through <i>dynamic pricing</i>. In the latter case, the heat price changes, e.g., every hour or 15 minutes in order to reflect the desired energy consumption [3]. A key prerequisite for attaining the full potential of demand-side flexibility through dynamic pricing is a high level of automation, e.g., through automatic building energy management systems.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	While the Danish node of AI-EFFECT already includes use cases related to district heating (focusing on (i) dynamic operation of district heating grids in response to dynamic prices and (ii) data-driven AI solutions for determining dynamic price signals), new AI-tools can be applied to fully address the aspects of heating-enabled energy flexibility that is described above

3.1.2 Data Center Management

Rationale:	Data centers are increasingly playing a major role in the bulk electric system, with some individual sites reaching sizes comparable to the largest power generation facilities.
Description:	<p>Combined with the aforementioned load size, the power consumption of data centers is extremely variable; this is due to, among other factors, the cooling system and the irregular usage by the end-users. Two key challenges in meeting this growing demand correspond to (i) enabling timely grid connections for data centers, and (ii) fully integrating data centers into the day-to-day operations of both current and evolving power systems [4].</p> <p>At this scope, multiple research activities have addressed the optimization of data center operations and their interactions with the electrical grids. At this scope, among such activities, several have developed and applied AI-based tools. The use cases that involves AI-based solutions for managing data centers from the power system perspective include: the forecasting of loads and power consumption (at server or data center level) [5], [6], the participation in demand response and flexibility programmes [4], [7] and the control of cooling and thermal systems [8].</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	Although the AI-EFFECT nodes do not include, in its project lifetime, use cases related to the management and grid interactions of data centers, the exploitation plan of the AI-EFFECT platform should aim at accommodating such use cases; in this regard, the inclusion of AI-agents focused on data center operations would be regarded with high importance, allowing to enhance the platform applicability.

3.1.3 Electricity Markets and Flexibility Services

Rationale:	The number of residential energy devices with smart capabilities is deeply increasing, revolutionizing the role of homes for energy distribution systems.
Description:	<p>Several EU countries are experiencing congestion issues with their electricity distribution infrastructures, limiting both consumption and generation of new energy resources. Flexibility, together with grid digitalization, has emerged as the key element to mitigate the problem and optimize the management of distribution systems, mainly via the shift or limitation of energy consumed or injected in the electricity grid. While the Danish node of AI-EFFECT already addresses the topic by testing dynamic price approaches (i.e., implicit flexibility), additional use cases are being implemented by the energy utilities and other stakeholders (e.g., aggregators, energy communities) for the direct control of smart energy devices (i.e., explicit flexibility), eventually via Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS).</p> <p>AI-EFFECT aims at expanding its set of use cases, including the test of AI-tools for the optimal management of flexibility commands, both at aggregated and smart device levels.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI technology has multiple applications in the electricity markets and flexibility services, allowing for various use cases. The AI tools will focus on different time horizons, hence working on various flexibility mechanisms, and technical scopes (e.g., energy forecasting, flexibility bidding collection, optimal control of home devices). Consequently, the AI tools will be responding to necessities of different kind of stakeholders: energy communities managers, energy utilities, DSOs, aggregators or HEMS developers.

3.1.4 Asset Data, Sensors and Alarms

Rationale:	The energy sector is experiencing a rapid growth of field data across transmission and distribution grids. While the data proliferation enable advanced applications, it also requires proper management of the vast data amount to provide real-time actions.
Description:	<p>The proliferation of Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices, with smart capabilities at the edge, as well as Intelligent Electronic Devices (IEDs), Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) and other sensors, form the technical basis for decentralized and distributed grid control solutions. Such devices provide a high amount of data that AI-based applications can manage with adaptive, context-aware processing layers beyond traditional rule-based systems.</p> <p>AI-tools can apply, for example: (i) intelligent filtering and prioritization, (ii) alarm validation and classification (for example, distinguishing true faults from noises or glitches), (iii) temporal pattern recognition, (iv) adaptive thresholding, (v) data quality management, (vi) predictive alarming.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	TSOs and DSOs have urgent necessity to deploy applications for the fast detection or prediction of faulty situation. The AI-tool ALLarMa [9], an LLM based tool for operational data developed using a graph model of the alarm dataset, can be applied for a new use case in the AI-EFFECT nodes.

3.1.5 Gas and Hydrogen

Rationale:	Europe's TEFs for natural gas and hydrogen are critical enablers of the clean energy transition. Electrolytic hydrogen facilities are steadily increasing in size and demand. One of the key challenges with electrolytic hydrogen facilities is the lack of unified platform to test and verify data.
Description:	<p>In the near term, facilities are delivering on urgent needs: proving that existing gas pipelines, storage systems, and industrial equipment can be adapted for hydrogen safely and effectively and improving core technologies like electrolyzers and fuel cells. In the medium term, TEFs are laying the groundwork for scaling up a continental hydrogen infrastructure – from large hydrogen production hubs and pipeline networks to hydrogen-ready power plants and industrial processes.</p> <p>AI-tools can contribute with testing new solutions, de-risking investments, training the workforce, and implementing/recommending policies. The ongoing work in these TEFs is ensuring that the hydrogen economy moves from experimental to mainstream, supporting Europe's broader goals of energy security, industrial decarbonization, and climate neutrality by mid-century.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can expand its use cases set, including the full innovation chain for hydrogen: from component-level testing (e.g., electrolyzers, pipelines) to system-level integration (e.g., hydrogen valleys, industrial decarbonization pilots), all underpinned by strong policy support and public-private collaboration.

3.1.6 Nuclear Power

Rationale:	Nuclear sector is undergoing a profound renovation thanks to the more and more prominent role being acquired by Small Modular Reactors (SMRs). The distributed presence of SMR will directly impact the bi-directionality of power flows in the electrical networks.
Description:	The modular and scalable design of SMRs makes them ideal testbeds for AI-driven operational optimization, predictive maintenance, and digital-twin modelling, allowing experimentation without risking large-scale systems. SMRs' distributed deployment across regions provides rich, diverse data streams, enabling AI tools to improve load balancing, fault detection, and dynamic scheduling in real time. SMRs also facilitate exploration of hybrid energy scenarios, where AI coordinates SMRs with renewables and storage for flexible, resilient grids.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT involves SMRs as key components of its nodes. Use cases can be related to: (i) apply TEF services for AI-tools that monitor and control the SMR operations, or (ii) test AI-tools that manage electrical networks with SMR presence.

3.1.7 Fault Location, Isolation, and Service Restoration

Rationale:	Fault management strategies, carried out by transmission and distribution system operators, consist of multiple stages: Fault Location, Isolation, and Service Restoration (FLISR). The accurate and quick deployment of such stages is fundamental to foster grid resilience.
Description:	AI can significantly enhance FLISR by enabling faster, more precise fault detection through real-time analysis of high-resolution grid data. Machine learning algorithms can predict fault locations and propose reconfiguration topologies, reducing outage duration and improving reliability. By continuously learning from historical and streaming operational data, AI tools can optimize switching sequences for isolation and restoration, minimizing customer impact. It also supports adaptive coordination with distributed energy resources, enhancing system resilience and enabling proactive maintenance strategies.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	New AI tools are emerging for FLISR management, as alternative to the deterministic- or heuristic-based ones. Use cases with AI-based FLISR tool will enhance the services offered to the AI-EFFECT stakeholders, especially DSOs and TSOs as well as AI-tool developers.

3.1.8 Dynamic Line Rating

Rationale:	Dynamic Line Rating (DLR) extends the static thermal limits of overhead lines by continuously estimating ampacity from real-time environmental and conductor conditions, enabling higher utilization of existing assets.
Description:	<p>To replace the conservative worst-case assumptions with situational awareness, DLR is based on, among other data, wind speed, ambient temperature, and solar radiation. Currently, DLR is applied in constrained corridors and pilot deployments using weather stations, sensors, and physics-based thermal models; however, its adoption is limited by data uncertainty, sparse sensing, model conservatism, and the difficulty of integrating volatile ratings into operational and market processes.</p> <p>AI-based tools can address these barriers by fusing heterogeneous data sources, learning latent relationships between weather, loading, and conductor behaviour, and providing probabilistic, risk-aware ratings. In this context, AI enhances DLR reliability, supports short-term forecasting of dynamic ampacity, and enables its safe coupling with real-time operation, congestion management, and automated control schemes.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT nodes would benefit from the inclusion of use cases on DLR. The project already includes use cases on congestion management for TSOs (Dutch node) and DSOs (German node); hence, DLR would directly complement such use cases, offering more comprehensive tools for improving system operators' needs.

3.2 New TEF Services

This section proposes new TEF services that could be added, in the medium-term period, to the existing set of 14 TEF services being developed and tested by AI-EFFECT. This TEF service has been selected based on the potential impact of its development as well as the readiness of its technology. Moreover, this section highlights the goal of alignment with other energy TEFs.

3.2.1 Sharing Services with EU Energy TEFs

Rationale:	Together with AI-EFFECT, two other projects are currently working on developing TEF platforms for the energy domain (EnerTEF and EnergyGuard as mentioned in Section 2 of this document). It will be necessary to align the achievements towards a unified Energy TEF service catalogue for Europe.
Description:	<p>While each project advances specific technical components, validation methodologies and sectoral use cases, the post-project phase will require consolidation to avoid fragmentation and duplication. The objective is to align architectures and governance models into a unified, interoperable TEF framework, with particular focus on establishing a common TEF service catalogue. Key steps include mapping and harmonising existing services, defining shared taxonomies and access conditions, agreeing on certification and validation procedures, and converging on interoperable APIs and data models.</p> <p>The ultimate goal is a coherent, EU-level TEF framework, which can be constituted by multiple TEFs, for energy AI solutions providing transparent, standardised and scalable services to industry and research stakeholders. This results in a common TEF service catalogue, whose services can be then deployed in different TEFs and nodes.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	While coordination and dissemination activities are already ongoing with EnerTEF and EnergyGuard, in the second part of the projects the focus will be placed on the alignment of technical outputs as well as governance aspects towards a common TEF service catalogue.

3.2.2 Image Processing

Rationale:	AI for image processing has reached high maturity, driven by advances in deep learning, convolutional and transformer-based vision models. State-of-the-art systems can now perform robust object detection, segmentation and anomaly detection under variable lighting, weather and perspective conditions.
Description	<p>In the energy domain, the image processing capabilities support the automated inspection of overhead lines, substations, transformers and auxiliary assets using drone, satellite or fixed-camera imagery. AI-based vision systems can detect early-stage defects such as insulator cracks, conductor strand damage, corrosion, vegetation encroachment or thermal anomalies when combined with infrared imaging. In the context of fault prevention, early anomaly detection supports predictive maintenance strategies, mitigating the probability of permanent faults, cascading outages and wildfire ignition risks.</p> <p>AI tools for image processing need specific datasets for the training, especially if related to the electrical networks.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	AI-EFFECT can expand its set of TEF services by offering the required datasets, which constitute the basis for AI-tool training. Additional TEF services on this topic includes the validation of specific image processing features.

3.2.3 Cyber-Physical Security

Rationale:	AI-EFFECT TEF services can provide a controlled environment to test the cyber-physical security of electrical networks in which AI tools are deployed, as well as the security and robustness of the AI tools themselves.
Description	TEFs can emulate realistic network operations while introducing cyber-physical attack scenarios, including sensor failures, adversarial inputs, and coordinated intrusions. AI-driven control systems are evaluated for their ability to maintain stability, resilience, and safe operation under such threats, while monitoring tools assess decision-making transparency and fail-safe behavior. Simultaneously, AI models can be stress-tested against data poisoning, adversarial manipulations, or abnormal operational conditions to ensure robustness, explainability, and compliance with cybersecurity standards.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	Given the increasing importance of cybersecurity, also for the critical energy systems, its inclusion as TEF service (for assessing electrical infrastructures or the AI-tools themselves) increase the completeness of the AI-EFFECT catalogue.

3.3 New Compute Technology

New compute technologies have been developed in the last years, and some of them have emerged as key ones with prominent applications. Such technologies, which are sector agnostic, have reached different maturity levels and have various impacts in the energy TEFs, as described hereafter.

3.3.1 Large Language Models

Rationale:	LLMs present significant opportunities across the energy sector, particularly as advanced decision-support and interaction interfaces layered on top of complex technical systems.
Description:	<p>In transmission and distribution system operator control rooms, LLMs can function as AI assistants that interpret real-time operational data, summarize grid conditions, explain alarm patterns and retrieve relevant procedures, supporting operators during emergency situations.</p> <p>For DERs and HEMS, LLMs can act as intelligent customer-facing interfaces, enabling end-users to interact with their energy assets through natural language. They can provide personalized recommendations for demand response participation (as currently done in the Portuguese node), electric vehicle charging optimization, rooftop PV management, and energy cost forecasting, while explaining tariff structures or regulatory obligations in accessible terms.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can test LLMs for factual reliability, hallucination rates, privacy compliance, and alignment with operational safety requirements. In control room scenarios, the TEF can evaluate human-AI interaction quality, response latency, and decision-support accuracy under simulated stress events. For customer-facing applications, testing can focus on transparency, consumer protection, and compliance with energy and data regulations.

3.3.2 High Performance Computing GPUs

Rationale:	High Performance Computing (HPC) GPUs have fundamentally transformed AI by enabling the training and deployment of increasingly large, complex and data-intensive models.
Description:	GPUs accelerate matrix operations and tensor computations, drastically reducing training and computation time. In the context of energy systems, HPC GPUs support large-scale power system simulations, probabilistic forecasting, climate scenario analysis, and cyber-physical stress testing. They enable hybrid modelling approaches that combine physics-based simulations with data-driven AI, improving accuracy and robustness.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can provide controlled access to GPU-enabled HPC infrastructures as part of its testing and experimentation services, allowing developers to benchmark performance, scalability, energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness of their AI models. The TEF can evaluate how models behave when scaled across multiple GPUs, assess computational sustainability (including energy consumption of training), and test robustness under high-load operational scenarios.

3.3.3 Hardware in the Loop Simulation

Rationale:	Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) and Power-Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) simulation technologies are increasingly adopted in the energy sector to validate components and control systems under realistic, real-time conditions without exposing the physical grid to risk.
Description:	With the growing penetration of distributed energy resources, smart converters and AI-driven control algorithms, HIL and PHIL have become essential for safely testing complex, dynamic interactions before field deployment. AI-based controllers, predictive maintenance modules, adaptive protection schemes and autonomous grid management tools must be validated not only for functional performance but also for stability, latency sensitivity, cybersecurity resilience and fail-safe behaviour. HIL and PHIL environments allow AI models to interact with real hardware under extreme or rare scenarios, including fault conditions, voltage instabilities or cyber-physical disturbances.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can establish standardized testing protocols, as services, for AI-driven controllers and power electronics, benchmarking response times, robustness and safety margins under controlled stress scenarios.

3.3.4 Blockchain for Data Sharing

Rationale:	Blockchain technologies are increasingly explored in the energy sector as trusted infrastructures for decentralized data sharing, transaction validation and coordination among distributed actors.
Description:	<p>With the rapid growth of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), prosumers, aggregators and local energy communities, blockchain architectures offer transparent transaction records and automated execution of smart contracts, enabling peer-to-peer energy trading, flexibility markets and secure exchange of metering or operational data.</p> <p>Given the need for data inputs, blockchain can ensure data integrity, provenance tracking and auditability, reducing risks of data manipulation or fraud. In turn, AI can enhance blockchain-enabled energy systems by optimizing transaction validation strategies, detecting malicious behavior, improving consensus efficiency and managing dynamic pricing mechanisms. The combination of AI and blockchain therefore supports decentralized intelligence with enhanced transparency and resilience.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can provide structured validation environments for AI-blockchain integrated solutions. Testing services may include scalability benchmarking under high transaction volumes and latency analysis for real-time control compatibility. Moreover, AI-EFFECT can validate whether blockchain-enabled AI coordination mechanisms maintain grid stability, fairness and performance under stress conditions.

3.4 AI-EFFECT Platform

This section addresses the needed changes for the full establishment of AI-EFFECT as self-sustaining entity which can perform TEF services and support energy domain stakeholders in the upscale and validation of AI-tools. Since the technical achievements of the AI-EFFECT platform have been already completed in the project lifetime, successive updates, in the medium-term goals, must involve the governance aspects.

3.4.1 Establishment of Governance of AI-EFFECT as a Self-Sustaining Entity

Rationale:	The successful impact of AI-EFFECT is determined by, as crucial point, its establishment as a self-sustainable entity that is economically maintainable without the Horizon-Europe fundings.
Description:	<p>To ensure continuity, neutrality and operational stability, the establishment of a dedicated non-profit association represents a structurally sound option. Such an entity could either operate as fully independent or be legally anchored to an existing organisation (e.g., the project coordinator or a sectoral AI association), provided that governance safeguards guarantee openness, transparency and non-discriminatory access to services.</p> <p>Irrespective of the legal form, financial self-maintenance requires a clear and effective business model. A service-based revenue structure appears most coherent with the TEF mandate, whereby users (technology providers, system operators, SMEs and research actors) pay fees for access to testing, validation, benchmarking and compliance services. This model should reflect differentiated service levels, infrastructure usage intensity and certification complexity, ensuring proportionality and fairness. Additional revenue streams, such as membership contributions, strategic partnerships or participation in new EU-funded actions, could complement service fees to stabilise cash flow and support continuous platform evolution. The objective is to create a financially viable, mission-driven TEF structure capable of maintaining technical excellence, regulatory alignment and sectoral relevance in the long term.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	The deliverable D5.3 “Assessment and Recommendations for the Governance, Ownership-Operational and Business Models”, part of Task 5.3 “AI-EFFECT business model and governance structure to ensure long-term economic viability” will defined the specific measures.

3.4.2 End to End Development and Deployment of New Nodes, Services and Use cases

Rationale:	The proposed new use cases and services described in sections 3.1 and 3.2, respectively, requires technical adaptations as well as governance rules for their approval, onboarding, development and interconnection to the existing framework.
Description:	<p>The creation of an AI-EFFECT Board is required as the central strategic and technical governance body of the new AI-EFFECT entity (described in Section 3.4.1). The Board would evaluate proposals for new services, use cases and infrastructure nodes against predefined eligibility criteria, including technical maturity, relevance to the energy sector, compliance with EU regulatory requirements and consistency with the AI-EFFECT interoperability architecture. The onboarding process should include a formal validation workflow, potentially subject to approval or voting by the association members, thereby ensuring legitimacy, neutrality and shared ownership of the platform’s evolution.</p> <p>From a technical perspective, the integration of new services requires alignment with the AI-EFFECT framework architecture and its interoperable building blocks, including the workflow orchestration mechanisms developed in WP3. In particular, new services and use cases must be modelled and composed through the AIoD Designer, ensuring compatibility with existing workflows, data exchange standards and API specifications. This guarantees that any extension of the service catalogue preserves modularity, composability and traceability within the TEF environment. Ultimately, the objective is to combine governance robustness with architectural flexibility, enabling AI-EFFECT to remain an adaptive, scalable and interoperable TEF for AI in the energy sector.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	The aspects elaborated above will be addressed in the deliverable D5.3 “Assessment and Recommendations for the Governance, Ownership-Operational and Business Models”.

3.5 Documentation

The medium-term phase of AI-EFFECT considers additional tools and technologies for the improvement of the AI-EFFECT documentation. These upgrades and modifications improve the user experience and aim at simplifying the use of the AI-EFFECT platform.

3.5.1 Multiple European Language Support

Rationale:	Providing multiple European languages for the AI-EFFECT platform, documentation, and GUI interfaces would significantly enhance accessibility, inclusiveness, and adoption across the diverse European energy ecosystem.
Description	Energy operators, SMEs, regulators, and research institutions often face language barriers that limit their ability to fully exploit TEF services, understand technical guidelines, or implement best practices. Multilingual support ensures that critical information—such as safety procedures, validation protocols, and AI tool usage instructions—is clearly understood, reducing the risk of errors, misinterpretation, or non-compliance. It also encourages participation from a broader range of stakeholders, promoting cross-border collaboration and accelerating the dissemination of AI-driven innovations throughout Europe.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	AI-EFFECT will identify priority languages based on stakeholder demographics and operational coverage, implementing multilingual documentation pipelines with version control, and integrating language selection options in the GUI and TEF interfaces.

3.5.2 LLM-enabled Knowledge Repository at Nodes

Rationale:	LLM-enabled Knowledge Repositories at TEF nodes can greatly enhance knowledge accessibility, operational efficiency, and collaboration across the Energy TEF ecosystem. Each node could host a dynamic repository that integrates technical documentation, validation protocols, experimental results, regulatory guidelines and operational best practices.
Description:	By allowing stakeholders—such as AI developers, system operators, regulators, and SMEs—to query the repository in natural language, the system can provide precise, context-aware answers, summarize complex reports, and guide users through standardized workflows. This reduces onboarding time, facilitates cross-domain learning, and supports consistent application of TEF methodologies across geographically and sectorally distributed nodes. Moreover, LLM can synthesize insights from previous experiments, highlight lessons learned, and suggest optimizations for ongoing validation campaigns.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT will start defining metadata and training / fine-tuning LLMs on node-specific and energy terminology. Feedback loops from users can then refine model performance, expand knowledge coverage, and integrate real-time updates from ongoing TEF experiments.

3.6 Standards and Regulations for Europe

The reliability of AI-EFFECT solutions depends, in addition to the technical validity of the offered TEF services and the complexity levels of AI-tools that can be reached, also by the up-to-date compliance with regulations and standards. As energy TEF, multiple nodes involve the interaction with electrical networks, at transmission or distribution level, hence requiring the alignment with the national network codes, aligned with the European directives.

3.6.1 Electricity Network Codes in EU

Rationale:	TEF services and use cases of AI-EFFECT must be compliant with the specific electricity network codes of the European countries of node locations; this compliancy is necessary to ensure the applicability of AI-tools.
Description:	Compliance with electricity network codes is a critical requirement for any TSO or DSO participating as a TEF node within AI-EFFECT. The AI-EFFECT entity must embed regulatory alignment into its operational and validation procedures, ensuring that all AI-based services, workflows and testing scenarios respect applicable grid codes, safety standards, and operational limits. This involves systematically checking proposed services and use cases against the relevant TSO or DSO obligations during the onboarding and testing process, and formally validating their conformity before integration into the TEF service catalogue. By incorporating this compliance step, the TEF not only guarantees technical interoperability but also supports regulatory trust, enabling safe experimentation and deployment of AI solutions on real electricity networks.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	Next phase of AI-EFFECT requires the validation of electricity network code compliance for the AI tools and nodes under test. This requires an initial analysis of network code requirements and their dependence/applicability to the use case under test. The grid operator involved in the node will complement the set of requirements and grid code implementation possibilities.

3.6.2 Regulatory and Standards Compliance

Rationale:	AI ecosystem is rapidly evolving, with a great multitude of new application and use cases. In parallel, policy and regulations have to be introduced and adapted to guarantee the rights of all stakeholders involved.
Description:	<p>Obligations stemming from AI-related regulations, as the AI Act at EU and national level, as well as forthcoming legislative instruments, needs further conformity assessment. Continuous regulatory monitoring and structured compliance procedures are therefore essential components of the TEF operational model.</p> <p>In parallel, increasing standardisation efforts from bodies such as IEC, CEN-CENELEC, ETSI and ISO are expected to define technical and procedural benchmarks for AI systems, including aspects related to robustness, transparency, cybersecurity and lifecycle management. The AI-EFFECT entity should ensure that its testing methodologies and workflows are progressively harmonised with these emerging standards, thereby strengthening credibility and cross-border interoperability.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	<p>Building on task 5.2 “Risk management framework and mitigation actions to ensure regulatory and governmental compliance for AI-EFFECT”, the entity should consider the compliance with new regulations or updated versions of the existing ones.</p> <p>Moreover, the verification of compliance with applicable regulations and recognised standards can itself constitute a dedicated TEF service. By offering structured conformity assessment, documentation support and pre-certification testing within a controlled environment, AI-EFFECT can position itself as a trusted validation hub for AI solutions in the energy sector, facilitating market uptake while reducing regulatory uncertainty for technology providers and system operators. Such service is already in place (e.g., with respect to the AI Act) for TEFs in other domains than energy.</p>

3.7 User Interaction and Community

The other existing TEF initiatives that are ongoing in EU, with European fundings, have already been introduced in the Section 2 of this document. In the next years, with the increase of energy TEF maturity and more attention on governance and self-sustainability of AI-EFFECT entity, additional cooperation and alignments are expected. The overall goal is to adopt all the necessary measures for fostering AI adoption in EU energy sector; this involves, in addition to the mentioned collaboration with other TEFs, also the interaction with additional stakeholders and users.

3.7.1 EU TEF Ecosystem Coordination – Non-Energy TEFs

Rationale:	In the medium-term phase, the interaction with TEFs in the other sectors will intensify. AI-EFFECT will benefit of the experience of such TEFs, which stands at a more mature stage, replicating the most successful approaches and improving the others.
Description:	<p>Alignments with TEFs established under the Digital Europe Programme (i.e., the CSA CoordinaTEF and the domain-specific TEFs CitCom.ai, AgrifoodTEF, TEF-Health and AI-Matters) offer valuable insights into governance models, service portfolio structuring, certification practices and business model implementation; in addition to the replication, AI-EFFECT can carry out sector-specific adaptation as required.</p> <p>Collaboration must evolve beyond informal exchange and periodic coordination meetings towards a more structured and operational framework. This could include the establishment of inter-TEF working groups on, for example, regulatory compliance, standardisation alignment and cybersecurity testing methodologies; the definition of common service descriptors to enhance cross-domain interoperability; and the development of joint pilot actions addressing cross-sector use cases (e.g., energy–mobility or energy–smart city interactions). Shared training activities, mutual recognition of selected validation procedures, and coordinated dissemination towards industry stakeholders would further strengthen coherence at European level. Such structured cooperation would not only accelerate the maturity of AI-EFFECT but also contribute to the emergence of a harmonised European TEF ecosystem for trustworthy AI.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	The AI-EFFECT entity - being established - will set up clear cooperation structures, as working group and task forces, with the corresponding non-energy TEFs to address the topics described above.

3.7.2 Build European AI Energy Community

Rationale:	The great proliferation of AI technology in the energy sector is affecting a large variety of stakeholder types: research organizations, energy utilities, grid operators, energy producers, end customers, standardization bodies, technology providers, OEMs, public authorities and policymakers, etc. Given the massive impact, an open and fair cooperation ecosystem is needed to ensure transparent achievement of heterogeneous agendas.
Description:	The scale and heterogeneity of these impacts make it essential to foster an open and fair cooperation ecosystem, where transparency, trust, and shared objectives guide technological development and deployment. In this context, AI-EFFECT aims to spearhead the creation of a European AI Energy Community, providing a collaborative platform that brings together energy-focused TEFs, industry actors, research institutions, and regulatory bodies. This community will facilitate knowledge exchange, harmonisation of testing and validation

	methodologies, joint development of cross-sector use cases, and coordinated efforts in standardisation and regulatory compliance. By building such a structured, inclusive ecosystem, AI-EFFECT seeks to ensure that AI innovations in the energy domain are developed, validated, and deployed in a way that balances diverse stakeholder needs, accelerates technology adoption, and strengthens European leadership in trustworthy AI for energy.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT will formalize the European AI Energy Community starting from the target groups of the communication and dissemination activities performed in project lifetime (Task 6.3 and Task 6.4).

3.7.3 Community Interaction and AI-EFFECT Benchmarks

Rationale:	To facilitate user engagement, accessibility, and transparency, the AI-EFFECT roadmap foresees the development and deployment of an Interaction Board. This board, designed as a Graphical User Interface (GUI), will serve as the central point of interaction between the platform and its community of users, including researchers, AI vendors, energy specialists, and policymakers.
Description	<p>Implementation of Interaction Board will strengthen user participation, foster innovation, and support the sustainable exploitation of the platform. The main features of the AI-EFFECT interactive board are described hereafter.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggestions and Community Feedback. The Interaction Board will enable users to actively contribute to the future development of AI-EFFECT. Dedicated functionalities will allow stakeholders to propose new use cases, submit ideas for improvements, and communicate directly with the consortium through structured contact forms. A voting mechanism will be integrated to prioritize proposed use cases, ensuring that the platform evolves in alignment with user demand and sector priorities. • Benchmarking of Use Case Performance. A key feature of the Interaction Board will be the provision of benchmarking tools that allow users to compare the performance of AI solutions tested on the platform. This will include metrics relevant to the energy sector such as efficiency, robustness, compliance with standards, and scalability. The benchmarking functionality will enhance transparency, support informed decision-making by end-users, and encourage vendors to continuously improve their AI tools. • Enhancing Engagement and Sustainability. The Interaction Board will create a dynamic feedback loop towards the user community. This interaction not only increases user satisfaction and adoption but also contributes to the long-term sustainability of AI-EFFECT, as the platform remains responsive to evolving needs. <p>The Interaction Board will act as a key enabler for community-driven innovation, reinforce transparency and trust, and provide structured input for future updates of services, business models, and policy recommendations.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	AI-EFFECT will start from existing, open-source GUI solutions for developing the Interaction Board, tailored to the TEF activities. Features of the Board will be added iteratively, from basic visualization of TEF services data until the most complex closed-feedback interactions.

3.7.4 Open-Source Competition Framework

Rationale:	Open-source softwares are, since several years, vital for many sectors. They foster the high-quality and quick development, thanks to its community of experts. Energy sector is also benefitting of such achievements, and dedicated open source software competitions, which promote development of new tools, are emerging.
Description:	<p>AI-EFFECT will act as a central hub for the open-source AI energy community, supporting sustainable development and the practical deployment of AI tools. Competitions for the development of open source software will be organized as part of AI-EFFECT activities. Such competitions will be fully open, providing public datasets, reproducible benchmarks, transparent evaluation metrics and accessible leaderboards to encourage participation and continual improvement of models.</p> <p>By promoting transparency, reproducibility, and the sharing of AI models and algorithms, the initiative will ensure that advanced AI solutions for energy optimization, grid management, renewable integration, and demand forecasting remain widely accessible and continuously improved.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT will leverage competitive frameworks, for example Codabench [15], to organize challenges that drive innovation, benchmark solutions, and foster collaboration between researchers, developers, and industry stakeholders.

4 Strategic Roadmap: Long-Term Goals (2030-2035)

The third phase of the roadmap spans the period from 2031 to 2035 and represents the consolidation and global expansion stage of AI-EFFECT. During this phase, AI-EFFECT will evolve from a European-centered infrastructure into a globally integrated, cross-sectoral reference framework embedded in the full AI development lifecycle. The TEF will no longer operate solely as a validation environment, but as a mandatory, interoperable layer of trustworthy testing, certification, and continuous monitoring for AI systems across critical infrastructures and industrial domains. The long-term vision is to position AI-EFFECT as a cornerstone of safe, scalable, and sustainable AI deployment worldwide, extending beyond the energy sector and beyond European borders, while incorporating emerging and disruptive technologies.

The specific goals are described in detail in the next sub-sections, corresponding to: (i) additional nodes and use cases, (ii) AI-EFFECT platform, (iii) new compute technologies, (iv) documentation, (v) AI TEF ecosystem coordination, (vi) international standards for AI energy.

4.1 Additional Nodes and Use Cases

In the long-term phase, AI-EFFECT considers expansions to extra-EU countries, as additional project nodes, and the inclusion of an additional use case. Rationale behind the inclusion of this new use case at this stage is the maturity level, expected to be reached by that technology, in that phase.

4.1.1 Extra-European Nodes

Rationale:	Expanding AI-EFFECT and the Energy TEF ecosystem beyond Europe represents a natural evolution toward a global validation infrastructure for trustworthy AI in energy systems. Many regions are currently developing their own smart-grid laboratories, AI testbeds, and energy innovation hubs, creating opportunities for interoperability and joint experimentation.
Description	<p>South America: its electricity systems are dominated by hydropower generation and large interconnected reservoirs. AI-based use cases could focus on hydrological forecasting, reservoir optimization, climate-risk modelling and grid resilience under drought conditions.</p> <p>North America: hosts several large-scale testing infrastructures for smart grids, cybersecurity and AI systems. Collaboration with its institutions would allow alignment of testing methodologies and support joint research on AI-enabled grid resilience and cyber-physical security.</p> <p>Middle East / Gulf: energy systems in the Gulf region face unique challenges related to extreme temperatures, rapid deployment of large solar installations and increasing interest in hydrogen-based energy systems.</p> <p>East Asia: East Asia hosts some of the world's most advanced digitalized power systems and large-scale AI research infrastructures.</p> <p>Oceania: Australia represents a particularly valuable experimentation environment due to its very high penetration of distributed photovoltaic generation and residential or large battery storage, as well as grid resilience in weakly interconnected networks.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	<p>Specific collaboration opportunities, regarding the points above, will be established with the entities described hereafter.</p> <p>South America:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEPEL (Centro de Pesquisas de Energia Elétrica) [16], the main power system research institute in Brazil;

- CIER (Comisión de Integración Energética Regional) [17], which coordinates technical cooperation among electricity utilities across Latin America.

North America:

- NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology), Smart Grid Testbed [18], for evaluating interoperability and cyber-physical performance of smart-grid technologies;
- U.S. Department of Energy, NSTB (National SCADA Test Bed) [19], which focuses on cybersecurity of energy delivery systems;
- PNNL (Pacific Northwest National Laboratory) [20] and Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) [21], for grid simulation, AI computing and power system validation.

Middle East / Gulf:

- KAPSARC (King Abdullah Petroleum Studies and Research Center) [22] in Saudi Arabia, which conducts advanced modelling of energy systems and market dynamics;
- Khalifa University's Energy Systems and Control Optimization Lab [23] in the United Arab Emirates, which focuses on smart grids and renewable integration.

East Asia:

- SGPRI (State Grid Electric Power Research Institute) [24] in China;
- KERI (Korea Electrotechnology Research Institute) [25] in South Korea;
- NEDO (New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization) [26] in Japan, which supports large national demonstration projects in smart grids and AI-driven energy management.

Oceania:

- CSIRO (Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation) [27];
- AEMO (Australian Energy Market Operator) [28];
- UNSW Digital Grid Futures Institute [29] .

These Australian organizations conduct research on distributed energy resources, energy system planning and virtual power plants.

4.1.2 Resilience for power systems

Rationale:	Resilience of power systems has become a highly relevant priority due to the increasing frequency and intensity of climate change–driven extreme weather events, as well as High-Impact, Low-Probability (HILP) events such as cascading blackouts, large-scale cyberattacks, or geopolitical disruptions.
Description	AI-powered threat detection and disaster response mechanisms can significantly enhance early warning capabilities and coordinated recovery actions. AI assistants for control centers can support operators with real-time decision support, anomaly explanation, and scenario evaluation under stress conditions. Moreover, large-scale, real-time network simulation environments enable anticipatory resilience testing, allowing operators to evaluate extreme scenarios before they materialize.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	AI-EFFECT will include this use case in its set, providing validated testing and experimentation frameworks that ensure robustness, safety, and compliance of resilience-oriented AI tools.

4.2 AI-EFFECT Platform

The roadmap envisions the full development of the AI-EFFECT platform within the beginning of medium-term goals. This is specifically applied to the technical software infrastructure, considering also the tools for smooth onboarding of new services and nodes. However, we expect that the entirety of governance aspects will be fully place in the long-term phase.

4.2.1 Monetization and Remuneration Mechanisms

Rationale:	In this long-term phase, monetization and remuneration mechanisms will be fully operational, transparent and performance-based, ensuring the long-term financial stability of AI-EFFECT while preserving its non-profit and mission-driven character.
Description:	A structured fee framework will be implemented, combining tiered subscription models for recurrent users with pay-per-service schemes for occasional access to specific TEF functionalities such as benchmarking, certification or advanced simulation environments. Pricing policies will be calibrated according to infrastructure consumption, computational intensity, validation complexity and required regulatory compliance depth. A formalized revenue-sharing mechanism will allocate income proportionally among node operators and technology providers contributing resources to the TEF ecosystem, ensuring fair remuneration and incentivizing high-quality service provision. Digital accounting and traceability tools embedded within the AI-EFFECT platform will enable automated cost allocation and usage monitoring. In parallel, strategic partnerships with international institutions and participation in complementary funding schemes will reinforce financial resilience.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	The monetization mechanisms will be derived and proposed in the Task 5.3 and concretized in the deliverable D5.3 “Assessment and Recommendations for the Governance, Ownership-Operational and Business Models”.

4.3 New Compute Technologies

Over the coming years, a new generation of advanced digital and cyber-physical technologies is expected to significantly reshape the development, deployment and validation of AI systems across multiple sectors. Beyond conventional high-performance computing infrastructures, emerging paradigms such as quantum computing, large-scale AI compute infrastructures (AI gigafactories), pervasive IoT ecosystems

and advanced robotics are projected to reach higher levels of technological maturity and operational integration.

4.3.1 Quantum Computing

Rationale:	Quantum computing is expected to reach a stage of early practical applicability between 2030 and 2035, as advances in qubit stability, error correction and hybrid quantum–classical architectures progressively move the technology from experimental research toward specialized industrial use cases.
Description:	<p>In the energy sector, quantum computing shows particular promise for solving complex combinatorial optimization problems such as optimal power flow, grid topology planning, market clearing, and large-scale scheduling of distributed energy resources. Quantum algorithms may also accelerate simulations of physical systems, supporting improved modelling of materials for energy technologies or more accurate power system simulations.</p> <p>The connection between quantum computing and artificial intelligence is emerging through hybrid quantum–classical AI models, quantum machine learning algorithms, and the use of quantum processors to accelerate specific stages of AI training or optimization. Conversely, AI techniques are increasingly used to improve quantum hardware control, error mitigation and algorithm design.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can play an important role by providing experimentation and benchmarking environments for early quantum-enabled AI applications. TEF services could enable developers to test hybrid algorithms that combine classical AI models with quantum optimization modules, evaluating performance gains, scalability, robustness and energy efficiency compared to conventional computing approaches.

4.3.2 Robotics

Rationale:	Robotics is increasingly being deployed in the energy sector to perform inspection, monitoring and maintenance tasks in environments that are hazardous, remote or difficult for human operators to access. Today, robotic systems (equipped with cameras, thermal sensors and other diagnostic tools) are already used for inspecting overhead transmission lines, monitoring wind turbines and solar plants, and performing visual inspections in substations or industrial energy facilities.
Description:	AI algorithms enable robots to perform automated defect detection, asset condition assessment, and navigation in complex environments using computer vision and sensor fusion techniques. AI-driven robotics may also support autonomous maintenance planning, fault localization in transmission infrastructure, vegetation management near power lines, and inspection of confined or high-risk environments such as underground cables, offshore wind platforms or nuclear facilities. In substations, robotic platforms could assist in routine operations, thermal inspections, and equipment monitoring, reducing the need for human presence in high-voltage areas and improving worker safety.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can provide valuable testing and validation environments for AI-enabled robotic systems. TEF services could include benchmarking of AI vision algorithms for defect detection, validation of autonomous navigation in complex energy infrastructure environments, and testing of human–robot interaction in operational scenarios. Hardware-in-the-loop and digital twin environments could simulate realistic grid assets—such as substations, transmission corridors or renewable installations—allowing developers to evaluate reliability and operational safety before deployment.

4.3.3 IoT Devices

Rationale:	By the 2030–2035 timeframe, the role of IoT-enabled sensing infrastructures in the energy sector is expected to evolve from simple large-scale data acquisition toward fully autonomous, AI-driven distributed intelligence across the grid. As the number of smart devices increase, federated AI architectures operating directly at the network edge are foreseen.
Description:	Advanced AI applications will increasingly perform decentralized anomaly detection, predictive stability monitoring, and self-healing grid functions through collaborative edge intelligence. AI agents deployed across IoT devices may coordinate through federated learning frameworks, allowing models to be continuously improved without transferring sensitive operational data to centralized platforms. This approach will support faster response times, improved cybersecurity resilience and reduced communication bandwidth requirements.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can provide experimentation environments for validating large-scale AI–IoT ecosystems under realistic grid condition. TEF services could evaluate interoperability among heterogeneous devices, benchmark distributed AI algorithms operating across edge nodes, and test resilience against cyber-physical disturbances or communication failures.

4.3.4 European AI Gigafactories

Rationale:	The emergence of European AI Gigafactories represents a major opportunity for the evolution of Energy TEFs. These infrastructures—large-scale AI computing centers built around high-performance computing (HPC) systems and advanced accelerators—are designed to support the development, training and deployment of next-generation AI models at unprecedented scale.
Description:	<p>Initiatives such as LUMI AI Factory [30] in Finland, Barcelona Supercomputing Center [31] in Spain, JAIF [32] in Germany, Meluxina-AI [33] in Luxembourg and Pharos AI Factory [34] in Greece illustrate the growing European ecosystem of AI-dedicated compute infrastructures. Many of these facilities are expected to support large foundation models, domain-specific AI training and large-scale data analytics relevant to energy systems.</p> <p>Energy TEFs provide a complementary function that gigafactories do not typically address: validation, benchmarking and real-world experimentation. AI tools developed or trained within AI Gigafactories can be brought into the TEF environment for systematic testing under realistic operational scenarios. AI-EFFECT services could evaluate performance, robustness, cybersecurity resilience, explainability, energy consumption and compliance with regulatory requirements when such models interact with real or simulated energy infrastructures. In this sense, gigafactories act as AI development and training hubs, while TEFs function as independent validation and certification environments.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT could therefore establish formal collaboration mechanisms with selected gigafactories to create a pipeline from AI development to trustworthy deployment. For example, developers training energy-related AI models on gigafactory infrastructures could directly access TEF services to validate their solutions against standardized datasets, digital twins, hardware-in-the-loop environments and cyber-physical stress scenarios.

4.4 Documentation

The long-term phase of AI-EFFECT will also allocate necessary effort for refining the documentation regarding the use, maintenance and expansion of its platform and the TEF services. Advanced tools and technologies will be implemented for maximizing the user satisfaction and the full exploitation of AI-EFFECT solutions.

4.4.1 Auto-generated video and training course

Rationale:	Auto-generated video tutorials and training courses provide a scalable, accessible, and engaging way to convey complex technical content, demonstrating workflows, best practices, and TEF procedures without requiring extensive in-person instruction.
Description:	AI-EFFECT will leverage advanced AI-driven content generation to produce video tutorials and structured training modules directly from existing documentation, workflow definitions, and experimental results. These courses can illustrate step-by-step processes for using TEF services, explain validation and benchmarking procedures, and showcase real-world examples of AI tool deployment in energy systems. The approach also allows multilingual delivery, enhancing accessibility and engagement across the European and global TEF community.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT will integrate automated video generation pipelines that convert text-based documentation, procedural scripts, and LLM-generated explanations into narrated, visually structured tutorials. Interactive modules can include quizzes, simulations, and hands-on exercises based on TEF datasets or digital twin environments.

4.4.2 User-Guided Process Interactions

Rationale:	User-guided process interactions provide a structured way for stakeholders—such as operators and AI developers—to actively participate in TEF workflows, guiding experiments, validations, and monitoring the results in real-time.
Description:	AI-EFFECT will enable interactive, user-guided workflows where stakeholders can monitor AI operations, adjust parameters, explore “what-if” scenarios, and provide real-time feedback during experiments. These interactions may include adjusting simulation inputs, selecting validation metrics, or guiding AI model decision pathways in a controlled environment. By combining graphical interfaces, conversational AI assistants, and integrated dashboards, users can engage with TEF services intuitively while remaining fully aware of the underlying AI-driven processes.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	TEF nodes will implement interactive platforms that allow users to participate in AI experimentation and validation workflows. Features may include stepwise guidance, contextual suggestions from LLMs, interactive dashboards with live data visualization, and the ability to trigger alternative processing paths or scenarios.

4.5 AI TEF Ecosystem Coordination

The TEFs will acquire fundamental position in the energy sector, as necessary pillar towards the implementation of AI tools. At this scope, foremost importance is associated with the cooperation among the various TEFs as well as other entities and initiatives with similar objectives. This cooperation materializes also with joint dissemination events, workshops and competitions for open-source AI tools developments.

4.5.1 Global Energy TEF Establishment

Rationale:	A strategic objective of AI-EFFECT will be the structured establishment of a Global Energy TEF, positioning the initiative as a neutral, non-profit coordination hub for AI-driven energy innovation worldwide.
Description:	<p>While AI development in the energy sector is currently implemented through fragmented collaboration models—ranging from in-house teams to academic partnerships and private consulting—AI-EFFECT can provide a centralized, mission-oriented framework that ensures technical excellence, regulatory compliance and long-term sustainability. By operating as a “Center of Excellence” for AI-based energy projects, the Global Energy TEF will support clusters of SMEs with shared access to testing infrastructures, validation methodologies and expert guidance throughout project implementation and maintenance phases.</p> <p>In parallel, a structured information exchange mechanism will be established to facilitate knowledge transfer among developers, system operators, research institutions and regulators, promoting best practices and interoperable solutions.</p> <p>The formation of an extensive AI–Energy global community will anchor the TEF within a broader ecosystem of stakeholders committed to trustworthy, resilient and sustainable AI deployment in critical energy infrastructures.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT entity will start with regular technical working groups and fora, shared repositories and coordinated validation campaigns, reducing duplication of effort and accelerate innovation cycles. Governance board will define clear pathways for the implementation of the measures indicated above.

4.5.2 Conferences and Workshops

Rationale:	Scientific conferences, bringing together academic and industrial stakeholders, are fundamental for advancing AI technology and ensure its adoption.
Description:	For a distributed ecosystem such as the Energy TEF, regular physical conferences and workshops strengthen trust among stakeholders, facilitate cross-border collaboration, and accelerate the uptake of tested AI solutions. They also enable direct interaction between AI developers, infrastructure operators, policymakers and researchers, reducing fragmentation and fostering interoperable approaches to validation and certification.
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	AI-EFFECT can assume a coordinating and curating role in this process. Concretely, it can establish an annual Global Energy TEF Conference as a flagship event to present validated use cases, benchmarking results and resilience testing outcomes. The project can also organize thematic technical workshops focused on specific domains such as grid resilience, AI compliance testing, edge intelligence or large-scale simulation. Dedicated sessions for SMEs and start-ups can promote inclusiveness and support technology transfer.

4.5.3 Monetizable Competitions

Rationale:	Open-source AI energy competitions within AI-EFFECT (Section 0) will evolve from primarily community-driven innovation instruments into structured, monetizable and globally recognized benchmarking events integrated into the Global Energy TEF framework (Section 4.5.1).
Description:	<p>While maintaining openness, transparency and reproducibility as core principles, competitions will incorporate sustainable financial mechanisms that reinforce the long-term viability of the TEF.</p> <p>Participation models may introduce tiered registration schemes, where basic access to datasets and benchmarks remains open, while advanced evaluation services, industrial-grade validation environments or certification labels are offered under paid tracks. Industrial stakeholders and infrastructure operators may sponsor specific challenge themes aligned with real operational needs, contributing financially while benefiting from early access to high-performing solutions. Prize pools, co-funded by industry and international partners, will attract top-tier global talent and increase visibility of the Energy TEF ecosystem.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF:	Long-term goal is to implement the winning solutions in the AI-EFFECT activities. These winning solutions may undergo formal TEF validation and receive an AI-EFFECT quality label, creating reputational and commercial value for developers and start-ups.

4.6 International Standards for AI Energy

Maturity level of AI, expected in 2030 and onwards, suggests that this technology will be fully integrated into standardization processes, while requiring continuous refinements.

Rationale:	Maturity level of AI, expected in 2030 and onwards, suggests that this technology will be fully integrated into standardization processes, while requiring continuous refinements.
Description	<p>As AI systems become deeply embedded in critical energy infrastructures, fragmentation between regional standards could create compliance burdens, limit market access and slow down innovation. Therefore, it is essential that European regulatory and technical frameworks are systematically aligned with international standardisation bodies such as IEEE, NIST and ISA.</p> <p>AI-EFFECT can contribute by transforming TEF validation methodologies, benchmarking protocols and resilience testing procedures into pre-normative inputs for standardisation working groups. By providing evidence-based performance metrics derived from large-scale experimentation, the TEF can support harmonised definitions for robustness, explainability, cybersecurity and safety in AI-enabled energy systems.</p>
Implementation guidelines for the TEF	AI-EFFECT will deploy active participation in joint technical committees, liaison roles with European standardisation organisations, working towards coordinated position papers that will ensure how EU-developed practices are technically compatible with international norms.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has presented a comprehensive strategic roadmap for the evolution of AI EFFECT as a long term, sustainable TEF for AI in the European energy sector. It articulated a structured vision across three time horizons - short, medium, and long term - covering platform deployment, service implementation, regulatory alignment, governance development, ecosystem coordination, and integration of emerging technologies. Together, these elements outline how AI EFFECT can transition from a Horizon Europe research project into a permanent, high impact infrastructure supporting trustworthy AI innovation.

At the submission of this Deliverable, the project has reached approximately half of its lifetime, with the core technical foundations already established and the demonstrator nodes actively progressing. The second half of the project will therefore be dedicated to completing the short-term objectives detailed in this roadmap. These include finalizing the AI EFFECT platform implementation, maturing and validating the full suite of TEF services, consolidating documentation and onboarding materials, and strengthening cooperation with sister energy TEFs and related EU initiatives. Equally important will be the advancement of regulatory alignment procedures and the reinforcement of user centric engagement mechanisms.

A key milestone in the upcoming months will be the definition of governance and business models under Task 5.3, which represents one of the critical enablers of AI EFFECT's long-term viability. The resulting framework will guide ownership, operational responsibilities, sustainability mechanisms, and remuneration strategies, ensuring that the platform remains functional, accessible, and continuously updated beyond the project's funding period.

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